

Regenerative City-Wide Inclusive Sanitation: Integration of Urban Development

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Abstract: The challenges of urban sanitation management seem to be taking on new dimensions even as efforts intensify to change behavior that increase human exposure and technological solutions. This paper aims to present a pathway for the systemic-integration of sanitation into urban development. Systemic integration could contribute to some urban aspirations such as renewable energy for zero CO2 emissions; zero-waste city; green buildings and districts, urban governance, leadership and best practice, as well as enhance the resilience and livability of cities. The frameworks of regenerative sanitation, citywide inclusive sanitation and regenerative urban development were used to propose a systemic integration of sanitation into urban development. A regenerative approach to citywide sanitation embedded into peculiar urban contexts was proposed to seek much more than reducing human contact and exposure to faeces and achieving safe management. It intends to go beyond ensuring sustainability and resilience of urban structures where sanitation will be considered a priority in the preservation, vitality and viability of cities, especially cities that pursue regenerative pathways. Urban development and regeneration planning will aspire to provide strategic growth through restoration and reparation of degraded and damaged socio-ecological systems rather than just maintaining the status quo or going back to a previous stable state. The overall outcome is the integration of regenerative citywide inclusive sanitation into urban development and management. The regenerative pathway to citywide inclusive sanitation framework can guide policy formulation for city planners and managers for effective and efficient coordination to manage and prevent sanitation-related crisis or disaster in a circular metabolic flow with particular emphasis on food, water, energy, ecosystem and economy.

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1. Introduction

Sanitation has been historically considered from its bad sides (Kootatp et al. 2019) and treated in the context of other 'important' resources (e.g. water, health, environment, etc) (Kootatp et al. 2019, Hawkins et al 2013, UN Environment 2017). But, indications from current analysis are that a paradigm shift towards approaching sanitation as a resource with inclusive and collaborative management will provide better results over the reactive exposure/reduction measures (CWIS 2018). With the increasing evidence of slow progress (only 300 million people have moved up the ladder since 1990 (JMP 2018) towards ensuring access to safe sanitation solutions in urban centres, especially in developing countries, sustainable urban development and urban regeneration projects could be more viable when sanitation is properly positioned in the planning process. The challenges of urban sanitation

management seem to be taking on new dimensions even as efforts intensify to change behavior that increase human exposure and technological solutions, there is still a wide margin between desired results and reality (Esrey 2001, Fam and Mitchell 2012, Lopes et al. 2012, Andersson et al. 2016a). Solid waste aside, by-products of human digestion (e.g. faeces and urine) and materials from other directly related human hygiene activities should be major concerns for city managers (Luthi et al 2009). An average human produces about 1.5 litres of excreta a day, multiply this by the possibly 100,000 – 20 million residents estimated per urban settings and the proportions are huge (Luthi et al 2009). This could be treated as waste (and the ensuing risks to health, environment, economy and livelihoods) (Cairncross et al. 2010, UNDP 2016, Bai et al. 2016, Schmitt et al. 2017) or resource (and the potential contributions to food security, renewable energy, ecosystem renewal, constructions, carbon sequestration, horticulture, livelihoods and the economy) (Winker et al. 2009, Tucci et al. 2009, Lehmann 2010, Anastasiadis and Metaxas 2013, Czischke et al. 2015, Zareba et al. 2016). The impact will have a rippling effect on all other sustainable development goals (SDG) and could erode the gains in other areas.

Meanwhile, sanitation conversations have often been restricted and confined to certain disciplines and circles so much so that it is often given a passerby status in the overall debates on urban systems, their management and development. Thus, proponents of urban sanitation remain fascinated with the know-how and how-to of related technology and infrastructure without due considerations for how they all synergise with other parts of the complex and dynamic urban environment (Kootatp et al. 2019, van Weli and Ronijn 2018, Cookey et al. 2016, Andersson et al. 2016, UNICEF/WHO 2015, Galli et al. 2014). Yet, sanitation involves key activities of urban population that produce by-products of human digestion (i.e. faeces and urine) and other matter (e.g. grey and hygiene water), which, although, have proven to be hazardous to public health and environmental quality if poorly managed (Cairncross et al. 2010), could also be a huge resource potential (when treated and rerouted) for the sustainability of cities and their populace (Murray and Buckley 2009, Murray and Ray 2010, Andersson et al. 2016, Kootatp et al. 2019). It is estimated that about 55 percent of the world's population (4.2 billion in 2018) now live in cities and this number is projected to rise up to 68 percent by 2050 with an expected 2.5 billion more urban dwellers (UN 2018a). Asia and Africa will contribute 90 percent of this projection with India, China and Nigeria accounting for 35 percent of the whole at 416 million, 255 million and 189 million respectively; and by 2030 there could be 43 megacities globally, mostly in developing countries (UN 2018a) and 230 new cities (UNDP 2016).

This overwhelming preponderance for city living raises urgent concerns for the quality of life, environment and sustainability. The New Urban Agenda (NUA) of the United Nations (UN) recognizes that this trend could provide solutions to some of the world's sustainability challenges (e.g. housing, infrastructure, basic services, food security, health) if well-planned and well-managed (UN 2017). Sustainable urban development (SUD) is then, considered critical in the race towards the 2030 sustainable development (SD) agenda, particularly for making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable (SDG 11) (UN 2016). Cities have become the centre of all major social, economic, infrastructure, organization and environmental changes and are projected to account for 88 percent of global GDP by 2025. They contribute over 70 percent of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and demand 80 percent of global energy consumption (UNDP 2016). This unprecedented representation is on just a fraction (0.51 percent) of the earth's land surface (although it is expected to increase by 1.2 million km², i.e. triple, by 2030) (UNDP 2016, UNDESA 2018). This indicates wide-scale interconnected global challenges that require innovative and resilient-solutions through and from within the urban systems' potentials and available resources (human, social, economic, environmental, etc). And so, if cities will be resilient and resourceful, they need to ensure adequate housing and standard of living for all, universal access to safe drinking water and sanitation; equity in access to public goods and quality services, natural resource and ecosystem protection and management (Lehmann

2010a, Nassar 2013, Nunes et al. 2013, UN 2017); and integrated city infrastructure (Li et al. 2017). However, the fact that most of the envisaged urban growth will be in developing countries of Africa and Asia poses connected threats and gains that could affect all societal and economic issues that would spiral over to the rest of the world (UNDP 2016). One compound concern that has the inherent capacity to make or break the aspirations of existing and emerging cities of the world is SANITATION.

This paper aims to present a pathway for the systemic-integration of sanitation into urban development studies, strategies and practice on a foundation of regenerative principles with inherent sustainability and resilient components using a five-pronged approach towards citywide-inclusive sanitation (CWIS): (i) governance and management; (ii) infrastructure and service delivery management; (iii) resource recovery, recycling and reuse; (iv) partnerships and participation; and (v) local economy, enterprise and employment.

1.2 Global Urban Sanitation Outlook

Sanitation targets are still way behind in spite of the ambitious agenda of the sustainable development goals of 2015 and as global urbanization rates grow exponentially, service has been sedate and discrepant (WHO/UNICEF 2019b, ADB 2018, Schrecongost et al. 2020). In 2015, an estimated 756 million urban residents lacked access to safely managed sanitation (van Welie and Romijn 2018, WHO/UNICWF 2015, Galli et al 2014), but by 2019, over 622 million city dwellers lacked basic sanitation (i.e. improved toilet/pit latrines) while 2.2 billion had no access to safely managed sanitation across the sanitation service chain (i.e. from use to treatment/disposal/reuse) (WHO/UNICEF 2019b, 2017, Gambrill et al 2020, Schrecongost et al 2020). By 2050, the global urban population would have risen from 4.2 billion (today) to 6.7 billion (UNDESA 2019) with most of the growth in middle and lower income countries, particularly in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa (WHO/UNICEF 2019b, World Bank 2018). This could increase the number of sanitation 'have-nots', especially at the bottom of the pyramid, if current trends continue (Gambrill et al 2020, Li et al 2017, Reymond et al 2016, Eraydin 2013), which could very well become one of the 21st century's most urgent challenge yet (Andersson et al 2016). In addition, the aging infrastructure in developed countries could pose huge threats to urban resilience. This pressure puts sanitation management at a tipping point (Reymond et al 2016) as it becomes more obvious that the conventional sewer system may not always be the most appropriate option for urban dwellers, mostly in densely-populated vulnerable communities (Peal et al 2020, Gambrill et al 2020, Schrecongost et al 2020, WHO/UNICEF 2019b, ADB 2018, Evans 2013).

Non-sewered sanitation systems, such as pits and septic tanks, are predominant in Sub-Saharan Africa and most of Asia (WHO/UNICEF 2019b, ADB 2018); there are, however, a few sewer systems in parts of some cities. But, regardless of the type of sanitation system, the failure rates in these urban centers indicate huge risks with urgent and immediate concerns (Gambrill et al 2020, Peal et al 2020). For instance, sanitation systems could compromise urban development/regeneration and pollute ecosystem services and functions due to poor designs, construction and installation, and/or damages such as cracks, leakages, and infiltration from flooding and other events (Gambrill et al 2020, Peal et al 2020, Koottatep et al 2019, Jenkins et al. 2015). Even where sanitation infrastructure is available, it would only serve a small proportion of cities' population (Reymond et al. 2016, Mara and Alabaster 2008, Luthi et al 2009).

Also, constraints of social-ecological-systems' (SES) and the reuse of recovered sanitation resources (Kootattep et al. 2019) have directed that sanitation discourse take a different trajectory towards potential benefits to society and the economy. However, weak governance and institutional fragmentations and overlaps coupled with financial inadequacies continue to be huge constraints present grave hindrances (ADB 2018, WHO/UNICEF 2017, World Bank 2017). Currently, sanitation infrastructure are at odds with core sustainability principles (Apul 2010,

Koottatep et al. 2019) across the globe. Developing countries also battle with poorly constructed, operated and maintained facilities (WHO/UNICEF 2019, Peal et al 2020, ADB 2018, CSIR 2007, Rodgers et al. 2007, WSP 2007, Cookey 2013, Kaminsky and Javernick 2015, Andersson et al. 2016, Cookey et al. 2016) and developed countries struggle with retrofitting and upgrading deteriorating and senescent technology (Delleur 2003, Wilsenach 2003, Bracken et al. 2006, Ashley et al. 2011, Brands 2014, WWAP 2017 Koottatep et al. 2019). All of which could be traced to implementation and management challenges (Norstrom et al 2011) such as rapid population growth (troubling for planning), socio-cultural diversities, resource constraints, increasing tenants than homeowners, technical and ecological factors, political manipulations, unclear policies, weak governance and political will, institutional and regulatory fragmentation and overlaps, un-prioritized investments, disregard for contextual urban characteristics, inappropriate technologies, unskilled manpower, absence of user interface, uncoordinated public sector and lack of integration into overall city planning (Gambrill et al 2020, Peal et al 2020, ADB 2018, Luthi et al. 2011, Panesar et al. 2011, McConville et al 2011, Reymond et al. 2016, Koottatep et al. 2019).

Sanitation infrastructure for most cities of the future could face a wall of resistance from financial drawbacks, inadequate energy supply, inappropriate technology, insufficient skilled manpower; contextual misrepresentations; poor maintenance/repairs and inadequate attention in urban planning; which could then impair progress and override gains (if any) (Reymond et al. 2016, Tilley et al. 2014, Bassan 2014). For example, an estimated 1.5 billion sewered sanitation facilities across urban centres of the world do not have adequate treatment measures and so produce effluents of questionable standards (Mara 2003, Baum et al. 2013) in the global north, aging sewered infrastructure that date back over 100 years suffer from performance deterioration that cause blockages and leakages that often result in infiltration and exfiltration, and poor service delivery (Brown and Caldwell 1984, USEPA 1991, Kemp 2000, Reynolds and Barrett 2003, Fenner and Saward 2004, Ashley and Hopkison 2002, Qasem et al. 2009, Luthi et al. 2009, Corcoran et al. 2010, El-Sheikh 2011, Diagne 2013, Ahmadi et al. 2015, Miszta-Kruk 2016, Andersson et al. 2016, Capodaglio 2017).

Meanwhile, majority of non-sewered sanitation systems (mostly in developing countries) are in dangerously unstable conditions that could eventually contaminate large and surrounding urban ecosystems (e.g. groundwater, surface water, soil, etc), particularly during heavy rains (Banerjee 2011, Jenkins et al. 2015). They are often improperly operated and maintained, poorly constructed with high abandonment rates of up to 42 percent due to failure and lack of standard facilities for proper faecal sludge management (FSM); and this carries high public health and environmental risks (CSIR 2007, Rodgers et al. 2007, WSP 2007, Norstrom et al. 2011, Cookey 2013, Kaminsky and Javernick 2015, Cookey et al. 2016, Koottatep et al. 2019). The introduction of innovative solutions piloted in some urban centres such as Jinja, Uganda (van Vliet et al. 2011, UN-Habitat 2012), Cape Town, South Africa (DWA 2008a/b, Taing et al. 2013), Wageningen, Netherlands (van Vliet et al. 2006, van Vliet et al. 2011) and Tanum, Sweden (Fam and Mitchell 2012) highlight some of the complexities of urban sanitation (Koottatep et al. 2019). Specifically, a survey of 39 global south cities with a total of 72 million residents revealed a mix of offsite and onsite (i.e. sewer and non-sewer) sanitation systems in operation and some cases of open defecation out of 51 percent used onsite systems and of this approximately 36 million, only 31 percent were eventually safely managed; and out of the estimated 33 million using offsite systems, about 57 percent of the faecal matter were safely managed. Only 42 percent of the total 72 million dwellers in these 39 cities end up with safely managed sanitation (Peal et al 2020, 2014, Scott et al 2019). The study also revealed that there were failure modes with both onsite (non-sewer) and offsite (sewer) sanitation systems, which posed threats to public health and the environment. These challenges could inhibit the positive progressions of urban development, especially when containment systems are directly connected to open drains or water sources (e.g. rivers, streams, lakes, etc) in densely-populated areas (Robb et al

2017), unsafe emptying practices endanger public health (Strande et al 2014), and leakages/overflow from sewer pipes impact public services and infrastructure.

Several studies show that the uptake of new technologies are often impaired because the designs and implementation were not integrated into the existing structures of targeted urban systems and so could contradict other interests within the overall sociotechnical regime and halt the progress of other urban regeneration processes (water supply, natural resource protection, aesthetics and public places, health, etc) (Hiessl et al. 2003, Panebianco and Pahl-Wostle 2006, Luthi et al. 2009, van Vliet et a. 2011, Norstrom et al. 2011, Luthi and McConville 2011, Fam and Mitchell 2012, Taing et al. 2013, Koottatep et al. 2019, Peal et al 2020, 2014).

Subsequently, major sanitation infrastructure deficiencies and management inefficiencies directly impact sustainable urban development (SUD) and urban regeneration (UR) as disrupted biological diversity and pollution affect aquatic ecosystem, soil and air quality, thereby unbalancing the fundamental integrity of the urban system's lifecycle that support agriculture/aquaculture, food production and nutrition, public health and hygiene, transportation and housing, education, socio-economic, livelihood, environmental and aesthetic quality as well as industry and the city economy (Corcoran et al. 2010, Piana 2010, Norstrom et al. 2011, Schutze et al. 2011, Cookey et al. 2016, WHO 2018). Consider about 1500m³ of faecal matter (exclusive of greywater, which is 20 times as much) released into the metropolis daily (Luthi et al 2009, Norstrom et al. 2011) and the ensuing economic costs accrued from rebuilding and rehabilitating failed, aging, dysfunctional and leaking sanitation systems and other infrastructure that these anomalies affect such as housing, road, etc; and then the disease burden on income, livelihood and productivity including education and mortality (Norstrom et al. 2011, Koottatep et al. 2019, WHO 2018).

The future of the world's cities could be really jeopardized if a proper handle is not designed for urban sanitation that operates away from the techno-separatist paradigm that relegates it to the bottom of the list of priorities or shrouded under the shadow of other concerns like water, health and environment. Faeco-phobic perceptions also need to be addressed along with misconceptions of the resource-potential of sanitation products; and then sanitation infrastructure and service delivery need to be contextualized in a systemic, holistic and integrated manner that links the entire system and process to the lifeblood of the city in order to contribute to food security, carbon sequestration, energy supply, horticulture, ecological sustainability and ensuring the aesthetic quality of the environment and public places in such a way that captures the psycho-socio-cultural-economic factors, governance and institutional framework, geographical and ecological features, territorial boundaries and stakeholders of the urban system (Luthi et al. 2009, van Vliet et al. 2011, Luthi and McConville 2011, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013, Brands 2014, Reymond et al. 2016, Koottatep et al. 2019).

Furthermore, a sanitation crisis can cripple cities economy, functions, socio-technical systems and wellbeing at all levels as it does affect (directly and indirectly) development gains and outcomes in other aspects and could exacerbate troubling concerns (e.g. in informal settlements), This complexity influences decision-making and overall development pathways for cities (UNDP 2010). This is a 'wicked problem' for sustainable urban development (SUD) (Rittel and Webber 1973, Hawkins et al 2013, UNDP 2016) and the fate of SDG 6.2 and 6.3 as well as 11 could be in jeopardy (Luthi et al (2009, Reymond et al. 2016) unless there is a conscious and deliberate integration of sanitation (service and value chain) into urban planning, renewal and regeneration processes. This will include a collaboration between different communities of practice e.g. sanitation professionals, engineers, architects, urban designers and planners, governance and management experts, water supply and energy, food, health and education managers and government at all levels to advance citywide sanitation that recognizes two things: (i) every

resident's non-negotiable rights to sanitation at all levels, gender, status and age; (ii) the socioeconomic and environmental value of sanitation to the urban ecosystem.

1.3 Global Urban Sanitation Agenda

The sustainable development agenda for 2030 aims to drive integrated transformative solutions that are inclusive, resilient and sustainable and balances the three dimensions of sustainable development (social, economic and environmental) in a drive towards more complex, universal comprehensive and ambitiously dynamic management of our earth and her resources. Specifically, SDG 11 targets the inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable management of urban systems in all countries by improving access to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services (11.1), ensure inclusive and sustainable urbanization and integrated planning (11.3) and then reduce adverse environmental impact from municipal and other waste management (11.6) among others (UN 2016). In 2017, the United Nations (UN) New Urban Agenda (NUA) presented a commitment to an integrated, cohesive, inclusive and sustainable future for all cities of the world with a five dimension pathway for sustainable urban development (SUD): (i) national urban policies; (ii) urban legislation and regulations; (iii) urban planning and design; (iv) local economy and municipal finance; (v) local implementation (UNDESA 2017). These two agenda are intricately linked to address the overwhelming challenges of global metropolitan centres as they thrive for better living, improved livelihood, decent job and sustainable urban systems for every city's renewal policy and strategy (UNDESA 2017, UN-Habitat 2018). In like manner, the SDG 6 aims to ensure that water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) are available and sustainably managed in all the world's cities with sanitation targets on access to adequate and equitable service provision (6.2), reduced untreated wastewater discharge (6.3) and increased recycle and reuse of wastewater (6.3) (UN 2016). The NUA seems to integrate this for cities by envisaging a future where there is non-discriminating access to safe drinking water and sanitation and equal access to quality public services, goods and infrastructure (item 13a) (UN 2017). However, NUA did not properly capture the impact and contributions of urban sanitation, probably because sanitation is often viewed from its adverse effects on society when systems fail and/or as a by-consequence of impaired water quality.

Also, the sanitation agenda for urban centres is not particularly clear in both considerations (SDGs and NUA) as to whether the target is just to reduce exposure and containment or capture and reuse sanitation matter or both. The focus appears to be on access and service provision (NUA-Item 119 and 120; SDG 6.2 and 6.3) and seems silent on the recovery and reuse in other sectors like agriculture, aquaculture, horticulture, groundwater recharge, alternative energy, etc. Although, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Sustainable Urbanization Strategy observed that to meet the SDGs by 2030, urban residents will need proper access to basic infrastructure and services such as water and sanitation, the document did not identify urban sanitation management as a priority but focuses on housing, energy and transport just like the NUA (line 15). The World Health Organization (WHO) WASH Strategy 2018-2025 seeks to 'substantially improve health through the safe management of water, sanitation and hygiene services in all settings' and the key guiding principle is to place public health protection as a high priority (WHO 2018b) in a general context. Meanwhile, the World Bank sees sanitation as key to its drive to end poverty and is committed to innovative solutions towards ending open defecation, service delivery improvement, sustainable disposal and reuse and urban sanitation (through the citywide inclusive sanitation (CWIS) initiatives). The aim is to ensure access to safely-managed services, resource recovery and reuse, adaptive, comprehensive and contextual approaches with long-term planning, technical innovations, institutional reforms and financial mobilization (World Bank 2018, CWIS 2018). The CWIS makes an urgent call for collaborative responses to citywide sanitation with particular recognition for key contributions to a thriving urban economy and integrating

with urban planning, renewal, governance and focusing on outcomes rather than technology (CWIS 2018). Apparently, the World Bank Strategy hinges on improving access to and harnessing the value embedded in sanitation matter and activities in partnership with urban planners. Nevertheless, all these strategies and the SDG/NUA agree that sanitation is a non-negotiable fundamental human right and every city resident deserves quality services and access. The need to incorporate CWIS into urban development and regeneration plans is the focus of this paper.

1.3.1 Rationale

To comprehend the double-edged impact of sanitation on cities' existence and development, and the global interconnections involved, a consideration of what could go wrong and what could go right is essential. This understanding is a key platform for integrating urban sanitation management into urban development in an effective and sustainable manner that captures all benefits for every resident across the aisle. Cities are dynamic and complex networks of different socio-ecological and socio-technical subsystems (Godschouk 2003, Ernstson et al. 2010, Da Silva et al. 2012, Desouza and Flaney 2013, Romero-Lankao and Gnatz 2013, Cruz et al. 2013, Meerow et al. 2016) with a population from a 100,000 to 10,000,000 inhabitants based on the boundaries applied (UNDESA 2018a/b/c). They operate as contextual and adaptive multi-systems that include social, economic, cultural, ecological and technical components with integrated and interactive processes (Meerow et al. 2016). But, the world's urban systems' propensity to put pressure on every side (social, economic and environment) has made cities vulnerable and unraveled from sudden and chronic disasters that impair sustainable development (Kessler 2011, UNIDSR 2012, Eraydin 2013, Li et al 2017, Coaffee et al. 2018). The increasing challenge of aging and inadequate infrastructure, most of which are unable to cope with threats from dense populations and pandemic disasters, but are linked together to deliver essential services to urban dwellers at different scales and levels as well as the complex interactions of all aspects of the urban system add to the risk potential. The expediency required to address urban vulnerabilities and ensure that cities are reliably positioned to survive unavoidable disasters and prevent other natural and man-made hazards has led to the call for resilience in development and management (Eraydin 2013, Rockefeller Foundation and Arup 2015, Meerow et al. 2016, UN 2017).

Urban resilience has now become crucial in preserving cities' social, economic and ecological footprints within sustainable limits and was described by Meerow et al. (2017) as *'the ability of an urban system-and all its constituent socio-ecological and socio-technical networks across temporary and spatial scales – to maintain or rapidly return to desired functions in the face of a disturbance, to adapt to change and to quickly transform systems that limit current or future adaptive capacity'*. Resilient cities are reflective, robust, redundant, flexible, resourceful, inclusive and integrated with the capacity to continue to function and survive even after stresses and unexpected shocks (Coaffee et al. 2018, Rockefeller Foundation and ARUP 2015). But, achieving resilience in our seriously dense and poorly equipped and serviced (mostly developing countries') cities can be an arduous task, especially with the ever present risk of hazards from failed, dysfunctional and senescent sanitation infrastructure and/or the effect that natural disasters can have on these facilities. In addition, the inter-dependencies of urban infrastructure and services can be a minus when broken wastewater and faecal sludge facilities release hazardous and pathogenic materials into the environment, which pollutes natural ecosystems, increases disease burden, troubles income, livelihood, education and local economies, erode other infrastructure (e.g. housing, roads, water etc) and disrupts the social networks within the city; not to mention the global reverberations (Luthi et al. 2009/2011, Raymond et al. 2016, Kootatp et al. 2019). All of these concentrate cities' vulnerabilities to sanitation related hazards as they are often exposed to often times overwhelming shocks and stresses like unexpected high demand (from population

dense areas) on infrastructure and services, which then cause breaks, cracks and leakages due to infiltration and exfiltration that cause pollution and other effects (Coaffee et al. 2018, Kootattep et al. 2019). The UN monitoring report for SDG 6 (UN 2018c) reveal that over 40 percent of domestic wastewater alone were released into the environment without treatment, which poses grievous implications to public health and environmental sustainability (Peal et al 2020, 2014). It also pointed out that the NUA agenda will require about 7.5 trillion USD in water and sanitation infrastructure investments by 2030 to satisfy existing beneficiaries and cope with future demands. This can seem discouraging and out of reach even as the focus of SDGs, NUA and other global agenda is on toilets and treatment, not circular processes.

Li et al. (2017) suggest that cities require infrastructure that are richly integrated, ecological, effective, comprehensive and multi-functional and connects all the various aspects of the urban system at scale to improve ecological integrity and sustainability that guarantee SUD. The concept of 'eco-integration in urban-rural waste management' was proposed as a way to effectively solve urban pollution problems. Urban sanitation is much more than toilets and faecal containment, and reducing human exposure and environmental contamination (CWIS 2018, Panesar et al. 2011, Norstrom et al 2011, Luthi et al. 2009, Reymond et al. 2016); besides vast households will continue to use onsite sanitation options for decades to come even with the inherent challenges of construction quality, operation and maintenance; as conventional sewerage would mean more money and effort that decision-makers can ill afford in the face of other crucial expenditures and could in any case be inappropriate in current realities (ADB 2018, Peal et al 2020, Schrecongost et al 2020, Norstrom et all 2011, Reymond et al 2016, Kootattep et al. 2019). It does not help that a large number of sewerage sanitation facilities globally operate below minimal standards and produce questionable effluents and some of these aged and difficult to fix infrastructure (particularly in the global north) often suffer blockages and leakages that pollute the ecosystem through infiltration and exfiltration (Mara 2003, Baum et al 2013, Brown and Caldwell 1984, Capodaglio 2017, Andersson et al 2016, USEPA 1991, Ahmadi et al 2015, Corcoran et al 2010, Miszta-Kruk 2016, Reynolds and Barret 2003).

It is, therefore, critical to establish an urban sanitation that works intricately throughout the operating system of the city and its boundaries in a seamless synergy among infrastructure, technology, management and people. In other words, just as CWIS (2018) and Kootattep et al (2019) pointed out, a radical shift from old paradigms to a synergistic SUD that integrates sanitation into the very fabric of the city's existence (Luthi et al 2009/2011, Reymond et al 2016, Kootattep et al. 2019). SUSANA (2017) identified at least 40 targets out of the 17 SDGs and four SDG 11 targets that sanitation could contribute to directly and indirectly. If city managers and urban planners, designers, developers, architects, and engineers consider sanitation not just as a risk but as a valuable resource, then perhaps the SDG 6.2 and 6.3 could be achieved by 2030 and a global crisis averted. This could imply that the future of the world's cities hinges on an integrated, sustainable, multi-approach and regenerative management system that works intricately with context-specific ecological characteristics and surrounding natural ecosystems. Therefore, this paper proposes an integrated and comprehensive citywide inclusive system of operations that imbibes the innate and unique features of the urban social-ecological-system and sanitation situation to regenerate and then sustain the resilient capacities of the city and its environs.

2.0 Conceptual Foundations

Regenerative cities where symbiotic resilience is designed into planning and management designs as well as implementation strategies will create the inclusive, sustainable and safe livable urban centers advocated by SDG 11. The provision of crucial urban infrastructure and services (e.g. water supply, solid waste management, food and energy supply, and sanitation) for residents should be planned in a systemic and integrated manner rather than in silo

approaches so as to ensure that there are interconnections between the sectors/subsectors that act as buffers and provide opportunities for shared responsibilities and profits (Li et al 2017, Axinte et al 2019, Pandit et al 2017). Several studies have highlighted the symbiotic relationships within urban systems and their infrastructural provisions and the surrounding ecosystems' services and functions. In essence, livable cities will have to operate within the urban circular metabolism of their unique contexts (Wolman 1965, Kennedy et al 2011, Decker et al 2000). Perales-Momparler et al (2015) proposed the regenerative urban stormwater management that considered interactions with other urban infrastructure management, and then Pandit et al (2017) and Li et al (2017) considered the benefits of linking all or major urban infrastructure as a single whole system and basing them on peculiar ecological characteristics. Axinte et al (2019) attempted to bring them all together in their conceptual framework for regenerative city-regions as they argue that cities could plan to work around their ecosystems and the needs of residents.

In the context of this, it becomes distinctly important to transit from the silo approach of urban sanitation currently practiced. It is even more so imperative to incorporate sanitation management into the structure of other urban services and infrastructure in a holistic, systemic and integrated manner. A review of the Asian Development Bank's (ADB) sanitation investment from 2012-2016 indicated that combining water supply institutions and cost recovery mechanisms with urban sanitation management allowed for high levels of implementation success (ADB 2018). As rising population threatens cities' holding capacities, the densely-populated areas where most of the poor, marginalized and vulnerable live in such close proximity with unfavorable sanitation facilities will be hotspots for sanitation disasters. The consequences of such disasters will spill over to other parts of the city and its boundaries, impact other urban services and infrastructure and then impair the ecosystem and public health. Over the years, many have called for a systemic integration of sanitation into urban development and/or regeneration planning, implementation and management (Luthi et al 2009, Reymond et al 2016, UNEnvironment 2018, Gambrill et al 2020, Schrecongost et al 2020, Hawkins et al 2013, Kootatpet et al 2019). With a looming urban sanitation and population crisis, there is no better time than now to intensify transdisciplinary research with interconnecting perspectives to explore solutions with contextual, inclusive and regenerative components (Girardet et al 2017, Woo et al 2010, Thompson and Newman 2016).

This concept paper aims to explore the possibility of incorporating sanitation into city plans and development processes from the early stages and at all levels. The intention is to create an alleyway for researchers, practitioners, academics and decision-makers to consider sanitation as an intrinsic part of the urban system, and thereby seek and produce adaptive, contextual and symbiotic solutions. Due to this broad stretch in consideration, interdisciplinary conceptual foundations were reviewed to develop preliminary ideas on integrating sanitation and urban development/regeneration. The concepts of **citywide inclusive sanitation** (CWIS 2018, Gambrill et al 2020, 2016, Schrecongost et al 2020), **regenerative sanitation** (Kootatpet et al 2020) and **regenerative urban development** (Thompson and Newman 2016, Woo et al 2010, Girardet 2017, Hes and du Pleiss 2014, du Pleiss 2012, van der Ryn and Cowan 2007, Resnick 2003) were used as anchors for proposing a regenerative pathway for citywide inclusive sanitation and urban development.

2.1 Regenerative Urban Development (RUD)

RUD applies the principles of regenerative design and development (Lyle 1994, 1996) from the built environment to the urban system and progresses from merely minimizing the damage caused by dependence on fossil fuels, eco-destruction production and consumption processes, socio-cultural inequities and discriminations, resource conflicts, (generally man acting like the lords of the earth), and maintaining a neutral impact or changing to certain trajectories (e.g. zero-emission) – to conscious and deliberate pursuits of restoration and recovery so as to produce

natural benefits for all the urban SES and residents in a symbiotic relationship between man (the chief) and nature (the force) (McDonough and Braungart 2002, Mang and Reed 2012, du Plessis 2012, Hes and du Plessis 2014, Thompson and Newman 2016, Axinte et al. 2019).

It has been suggested that RUD could be a better option for developing livable and resilient cities that sustain their equilibrium and integrity holistically and capacity to withstand and recover from stress and pressure of all kinds (Rockefeller Foundation 2014). Arguably, it could be a more appropriate path towards improving degraded social-ecological-systems globally and pushing towards SDG 11's safe, inclusive, sustainable and resilient cities that respect all rights and provide benefits to all residents in the present and future without any form of discrimination (UN 2016, UN-Habitat 2017). According to Girardet et al. (2014), RUD aims to assure that we develop comprehensive strategies for an enhancing and restorative relationship between an urbanizing humanity and the ecosystems that provide the resources from our sustenance. In view of sustainable urban regeneration (SUR), which is described as *'regeneration actions, policies and processes within a city, which addresses interrelated technical, spatial and socio-economic problems in order to reduce environmental impacts, mitigate environmental risks and improve environmental quality of urban systems, lifestyles and assets'* (URBACTII 2015); RUD seeks resource generation, natural capital, ecosystems' restoration, and built spaces in conjunction with infrastructure, community and social regeneration (Boselli 2016, Axinte et al. 2019) and eco-regeneration (Girardet 2017). From a regenerative paradigmatic view, urban regeneration (UR) could be a tool for comprehensive and integrated planning and design towards rehabilitation and/or (re)development of a city with the aim to restore and sustain economic, social, environmental and physical conditions for existing and future residents (Robert and Sykes 2000, Jones and Evans 2008). It should not just focus on the physical environment (i.e. infrastructure and other provisions for service delivery), but also on quality of life for residents (i.e. housing, healthcare, air quality, education, public spaces, etc), social welfare (i.e. basic social services), economic opportunities (i.e. income, livelihood, employment, enterprise, revenue, etc), and governance (i.e. inclusive policies and institutions, multi-stakeholders partnerships and involvements, etc) whether it is to develop new areas or restore/improve existing ones (Tallon 2009, Jones and Evans 2008, Nunes et al 2013) to ecosystem restoration and biophilic cooperation.

Regenerative urban systems are, therefore, cities that relate symbiotically with the surrounding ecosystems and hinterlands to maintain resource flow and continued existence. These regenerative cities (RC) should focus not just on reducing ecological footprints, ensuring environmental sustainability and zero emissions to reduce further damage, but also on environmentally enhancing and restoring degraded natural systems, energy-efficient renewable energy and visionary governance and stakeholders' involvement and partnerships. These biophilic and ecophilic cities (Beatley and Newman 2013, Girardet 2017) are also expected to develop within the integrity of planetary ecosystem boundaries and the place context in order not to compromise resilience and future conditions (Massey 1993, Woo et al. 2010, Thompson and Newman 2016, Girardet 2017, Girardet et al. 2017, Asinte et al. 2019). In addition, compactness and integrated management/structures, local level processes, waste recycling and reuse, proximity and internalization sourcing and production as well as urban-rural linkages will make these urbanized areas more likely to serve the purpose of retracing the negative impacts on our planet and also guarantee a safe, resilient, inclusive, sustainable and productive habitation for urban dwellers globally (Lehman 2016, Girardet et al. 2017, UN-Habitat 2017b, Axinte et al. 2019). The outcome of such urban socio-ecological system (SES) would benefit local enterprises and job markets, cities' economy, livelihood and income, social and individual well-being, and governance as new businesses and gains are established.

2.2 Regenerative sanitation (ReGenSan) and Citywide Inclusive Sanitation (CWIS)

Most cities' linear metabolism and silo approaches to sanitation management challenge progress even when applying sustainable solutions. The reuse and regenerating potential of sewage and faecal sludge are untapped and disposed of (mostly through unsafe practices and failing facilities) instead of been reintroduced into the urban system for reuse as fertilizer, husbandry, horticulture, and forest development (Girardet 2017, Kootattep et al. 2019). The fact that technology and management solutions are often single-focused and handled in isolation of other parts of the urban system belies the impact-connections that could paralyze city centres and surroundings. For example, dysfunctional onsite sanitation systems (e.g. broken septic tanks or aged and cracked sewer systems) can pollute ground and surface water sources, and agricultural soil as well as degrade the ecosystem, air and odour quality, roads and building infrastructure among others; which all culminate in related health and environmental hazards that affect a municipality's social and economic well-being. With an impending urban sanitation crisis (and the cross-boundary impacts imminent), it cannot continue to be business as usual. The Kootattep et al. (2019) regenerative sanitation adopts the systemic-ecological worldview rather than the regular reductionist-mechanistic perspective of most sanitation concepts (Capra 1997/2002, du Plessis and Brandon 2015, Kootattep et al. 2019). It is structured on the theories of functionalism and systems (Von Baertalaffy 1956/1968, Mooney et al. 2013, Sato 2011), and centralization and decentralization (Wilderer and Schreff 2000, Tchobanoglus et al. 2009, Bieker et al. 2010, IDRC 2010, Larsen and Manurer 2011, Libralato et al. 2012, Tchobanoglous and Leverenz 2013) to build a holistic, integrated, systemic and functional foundation for a new way of thinking sanitation. They argue that sanitation is regenerative when it integrates psycho-social factors and ecosystem resilience with resource recovery and technological elements based on well-defined infrastructure standard specifications for rejuvenated and revitalized solutions that mimic and contribute to natural systems (Kootattep et al. 2019).

This transition from linear degenerated systems to regenerative cycles could strengthen and accelerate the SDG 6 agenda while also ensuring water and energy efficiency and renewable energy production, revitalize and reintegrate social-ecological systems, support regenerative agriculture and food sufficiency, enhance resource recycling and reuse and particularly support regenerative cities circular metabolism and resilience, local livelihoods and economy, health and social well-being, as well as stakeholders' partnerships (Cole et al. 2012, Kootattep et al. 2019). They proposed 10 key principles that operate in systemic and integrated networked connections – co-related with the other principles of place-based development. The principles (see Table 1) provide an opportunity for new ways to learn about urban sanitation, seek fresh answers from old ways, adapt to change with resilience and flexibility, think, then act and work to integrate and synergize the entire urban sanitation management process as a whole system (and not just working from individual parts); and it is only when these principles are imputed together that they give desired results. ReGenSan sees sanitation as resource, service and products development and management rather than problem management. It aims to reduce the transfer of burden from urban sanitation management, provide sanitation-derived products and services, incorporate restoration/rehabilitation, and ensure continuous improvements.

Table 1 Summary of ReGenSan principles and interpretation

S/No	Regenerative sanitation principles	Summary Interpretation
1	Appropriate technology (ApT)	Technology that is appropriate for particular 'place' and 'scale'
2	Biomimicry and Biophilia (BaB)	Sanitation solutions/strategies that mimic and support natural systems
3	Fit-for-purpose governance (FPG)	Governance mechanisms that fit the place and scale and purpose for functional, efficient and effective sanitation requirement
4	Hybridized solutions (HS)	Sanitation solutions that could synergize centralized and decentralized options to deliver effective and efficient services to particular 'place' and 'scale'.
5	No-transfer-of-burden (NToB)	Sanitation solutions that do not transfer health, environment, social, economic and ecological burdens to society
6	Systemic holistic integration (SHI)	Sanitation solutions that interconnect and synergize subsystems, dimensions and components to achieve functional, efficient, and effective whole systems
7	Place and scale (PaS)	Sanitation solutions that indigenously align to location (place) and sites (scale) for optimization
8	Participation and partnership (PaP)	Sanitation solutions that involve stakeholders at all spheres and levels of localized contexts
9	Recycling and safe reuse (RaSR)	Sanitation solutions that recover and safely reuse valuable resources by-products of human digestion.
10	Rehabilitation of dysfunctional facilities (RoDF)	Sanitation solutions that rehabilitate and retrofit dysfunctional. Unimproved and aging infrastructure

This interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary framework is unique in that it is applicable to both developed and developing countries, and to all stages, processes and cycles for delivering sanitation solutions and contributes to an understanding of sanitation's complex-dynamic, systemic and integrated roles in regenerative urban development. It is based on an ecological worldview wrapped around 'place' and 'scale' focus where comprehensive sanitation solutions are provided within sani-sheds (i.e. sanitation systems should be tailored to the unique features of the 'place' by exploring the opportunities and solutions that are indigenously akin to the specific 'place' (location), 'scale' (site) and context). In other words, urban sanitation management should be committed to sani-sheds by ensuring that issues such as wastewater, sewage and faecal sludge management, resource recovery, etc., are contained and managed within their sphere of influence, thus reducing material transfer for treatment at other locations. It provides a functional and progressive approach towards improving and expanding access to sanitation services at a 'scale' in cities by achieving net-benefits for all relevant actors (Potter et al. 2011, Kvarnström 2011).

However, with the accumulated risks of failing, aging and damaged urban sanitation infrastructure globally, particularly in the South and the additional threats from a burgeoning city population, planning for regenerative cities must include protecting residents and the surrounding ecosystem from a sanitation-related disaster. This correlates with the CWIS call for new approaches to urban sanitation with a paradigm shift from conventional and centralized (sewer) focus to a balance that embrace services and targets partnership, BOPs and other vulnerable groups. The World Bank, BMGF and other stakeholders in a bid to find new ways to consider urban sanitation (CWIS 2018, Narayanan et al. 2018). The CWIS framework is a public service approach to plan and implement urban sanitation across the sanitation service chain (SSC) that is safe, adequate, equitable and sustainable for

everyone in the city where recovery and reuse is a part of the system within comprehensive and hybrid approaches that are adaptive, flexible, contextual and incremental, and then harmonized with other related urban services in such a way that contributes to a thriving urban economy (Schrecongist et al. 2020, Gambrell et al. 2020, ADB 2018, Kootattep et al 2019, Narayan and Luthi 2019). Gambrell et al. (2020) encourages governments to focus on service provision rather than infrastructure development in implementing CWIS via the mixed lenses of finance, institutions, policies, regulations, socio-economics and environment. The World Bank also uses an interdisciplinary approach to also work governments to harmonize sanitation solutions with other related urban services and promotes design decisions that are driven by both capital and operational expenditures. Meanwhile, Schrecongist et al. (2020) argue that CWIS is already agnostic about technology-choice as the preferred and appropriate technology is often dependent on peculiar variations of different urban contexts. They further argue that CWIS must be organized as a public service without completely excluding the private sector. In other words, government need to direct and regulate private sector participation by providing entering rules for safety and inclusion and creating market incentives for investments and innovations. This requires a CWIS service framework that covers core services outcomes (i.e. equity, safety, and sustainability), which will be achieved through system functions (i.e., responsibility, accountability and resource planning and other management) towards achieving relevant and contextual public service delivery systems for urban sanitation (Schrecongist et al. 2020).

Effects to apply utility and urban service concepts to urban sanitation have not made much in-road in practice, and so the CWIS service framework aims to offer a simplified, but coherent conceptual frame for public service delivery systems that mainstream low-income communities' needs and a range of appropriate technologies, service models and governance mechanisms (Schrecongist et al. 2020). However, CWIS is still relatively new in the practice and study of sanitation (Schrecongist et al. 2020) and some even consider it to be a reframing of sustainable urban sanitation (Narayan and Luthi 2019). But, proponents argue that the holistic and inclusive elements puts CWIS on a separate scale even though it may take a while for its value in practice, service and outcomes to be ascertained (Narayan and Luthi 2019, Schrecongist et al. 2020).

The Kootattep et al. (2019) Sanitation 4.0's (of the ReGenSan framework) urban sanitation special consideration takes the CWIS further by suggesting that urban regeneration (UR) and sanitation could be complementary in the pursuit of universal coverage, especially as it concern BOPs. The aim is a unified front that supports cities' drive towards food security, sustainable energy supply, urban greening, zero waste emissions, environmental protection and improved services/expanded access. It is resource-based and considers sanitation processes as a production factory that could provide high-quality biomass resources to serve various aspects of urban systems (Esrey 2001, Winker et al. 2009, Zareba et al. 2016, Kootattep et al. 2019). This will demand a strategy that operates continuous. Improvement of functional existing urban sanitation infrastructures, retrofitting of dysfunctional and/or damaged facilities and producing innovative solutions that incorporate resource recovery and reuse across the peculiar context of urban systems. The message is to encourage urban planners and developers to embed core sanitation expectations into urban blueprints so as to develop strategies that harness potentials from sanitation rather than a sanitation crisis that could preclude disaster for the city. The authors propose that Sanitation 4.0 Platform offers holistic, integrated, systemic and multi-transdisciplinary perspectives to drive innovations, research, management, planning, technology, governance and ecosystem sustainability and deliver on the following (Kootattep et al. 2019):

- I. Improved urban service and access expansion of safely-managed sanitation infrastructure that delivers functional, effective and optimal performance (whether sewerage and non-sewerage)
- II. Retrofitted and upgrade unimproved failed, dysfunctional and abandoned sanitation infrastructure in developing countries' cities and rehabilitated poorly performing and aging sewerage systems in developed countries;

- III. Redesign existing urban sanitation infrastructural systems to be more regenerative by adopting technologies and processes that are systemic integrating and contextual (e.g. integrate eco-efficiency and ecological-based approaches; recover and reuse value-added resources, mimic natural systems, plan with urban sani-sheds); and
- IV. Support local physical, socioeconomic, cultural, spatial and decision-making structures of specific cities for appropriate and best applicable technology and management solutions because a dissonance between users, service providers, institutions, ecosystems, and infrastructure can halt even the best of plans and implementation.

This paper uses the regenerative urban development and blend of regenerative sanitation and CWIS frameworks (Table 2) to propose a regenerative citywide inclusive sanitation for urban development and management.

Table 2: Regenerative Sanitation and City-Wide Inclusive Sanitation Platforms

Regenerative Sanitation 4.0 Urban Sanitation Platform (Kootattep et al. 2019)	City-Wide Inclusive Sanitation Platform Building Blocks (Schrecongist et al. 2020)
Ensure infrastructural standardizations, especially with non-sewered sanitation systems in cities of developing countries	Prioritization of the right of all to sanitation with inclusive strategies reaching informal settlements and vulnerable populations
Ensure that urban sanitation infrastructure delivers products and services, particularly in harnessing resources from sanitation systems to support urban cities' renewables energy, local food supply, value chain and green landscapes	Delivery of 'safe management' along the entire sanitation service chain by focusing on service outcomes rather than technologies, and by embracing innovation and incrementalism
Ensure that urban sanitation solutions are designed to address cities population at the base-of –the pyramid (BoP)	Recognition of sanitation as contribution to a thriving urban economy by integrating sanitation into urban planning reforming regulatory policies, and embracing resource recovery and reuse
Ensure that urban sanitation infrastructure aligns with urban landscape to support biodiversity by mimicking nature's modes, processes and ecosystem, and adapting them to solve sanitation challenges	Commitment to work in partnership across sectors and stakeholders to make progress through clear institutions with accountability, embedding sanitation within urban governance systems

- I. Equity – everyone benefits from safe, affordable and equitable urban sanitation services that do not restrict by gender, socioeconomic status, location, ethnicity, disabilities, etc
- II. Safe management – environmental and public health are protected by ensuring that human waste is safely managed along the full spectrum of the sanitation service chain from containment to reuse and disposal
- III. Hybrid system – appropriate and contextual solutions that combine non-sewer and sewer as well as centralized and decentralized systems and harness the resource recovery and reuse potentials of individual cities
- IV. Clear mandates – mandate for urban sanitation is clearly defined with inclusive strategies, performance targets sufficient resources, monetary requirement and accountability
- V. Comprehensive long-term planning – short and long-term holistic and inclusive planning with participation from all stakeholders, incremental perspectives, performance incentives, and investments based on real-time activity, climate change, water and energy constraints
- VI. Complementary urban services – coordinating with other urban services, investments and development goals e.g. water supply, storm water and greywater management, solid waste management, water resources management, roads and transport, etc
- VII. Mixed business models and investment strategies – incremental and integrated investments that prioritize

safety, equity and sustainability which could be deployed via a range of business models to efficiently and equitably reach all segments of a city's socioeconomic strata as well as provision for non-infrastructure aspects of service delivery (e.g. capacity building, sanitation marketing, etc)

VIII. Governance and political will – well aligned institutional arrangement for operation and maintenance of the whole sanitation service chain and political commitment to safe and inclusive urban sanitation exhibited at all levels of government with local technical and managerial leadership and independent and autonomous performance regulators and service entities that are supported to make effective institutional reforms and enforcement. (Schrecongist et al. 2020, Gambriell et al. 2020, Narayan and Luthi 2019)

3.0 Regenerative Citywide Inclusive Sanitation

Sanitation management in urban renewal or new development projects will be adequately considered to control risks to public health and environmental quality. In addition, sanitation-derived products and other sanitation-related services could supply resources for greening cities, livelihood support, food production and food security. The concept of continuous improvement will maintain the functionality of existing safely-managed urban sanitation facilities and retrofitting of dysfunctional and failed facilities towards zero-waste emissions, wastewater recycling and environmental protection (Kootattep et al. 2019). Urban development and built environment is not just about the astonishingly dynamic infrastructure and technical complexities; there is also a large population that engage in more toilet and hygiene-related activities than any other human-biophysical activities in their lifetime, and this impacts life and society. In essence, SDG 11 concepts should incorporate the sanitation targets of SDG 6 to achieve inclusive, safe and resilient cities, as well as resource-based systems (Table 3).

Specifically, this systemic integration could contribute to some urban aspirations: (i) renewable energy for zero CO₂ emissions; (ii) zero-waste city; (iii) landscape, gardens and urban biodiversity; (iv) local and sustainable materials with less embodied energy; (v) density and retrofitting of existing districts; (vi) green buildings and districts, using passive design principles; (vii) local food and short supply chain; (viii) urban governance, leadership and best practice; (ix) education, research and knowledge; and (x) strategies for cities in developing countries (Lehmann 2010a,b); as well as enhance the resilience and livability of cities, land use and urban forms, innovative housing strategies/ sustainable building practices, sustainable transportation, urban ecology and greenery, recycling and upcycling, energy conservation and renewable energy, and sustainable economy/governance (Beatley 2015, 2012a,b, 2005).

At this juncture, it is profitable for city managers, urban planners, urban sanitation professionals, government and residents strongly consider integrating sanitation into urban development and regeneration projects so as to (i) reduce public health risks; (ii) support local economy and livelihoods; (iii) reduce carbon and water footprints; (iv) support food security and sufficiency; (v) protect and conserve ecosystem services, functions and natural resources; (vi) recover, recycle and reuse; (vii) local government management and stakeholder involvement; (viii) citizen and business community partnerships; and (ix) target population at the base-of-the-pyramid. A regenerative systemic-integrated pathway towards building an urban sanitation design that fits into the SDGs 6 and 11 aspirations will have to be strategic and well-thought-out; it cannot be a quick-fix. A transformation pathway that combines both RUD and ReGenSan principles and concepts towards an intrinsic whole approach to achieve the considerations above should look at key aspects as they impact and influence each city's unique peculiarities. Table 4 presents key considerations for comprehensive long-term and multi-scale planning for regenerative-citywide-inclusive- sanitation (Reg-CWIS).

4.0 The Regenerative Pathway to Citywide-Inclusive Sanitation (Reg-CWIS)

A regenerative approach to citywide sanitation embedded into peculiar urban contexts will seek much more than reducing human contact and exposure to faeces and achieving safe management, it will also aim to go beyond ensuring sustainability and resilience of urban structures. Sanitation will be considered a priority in the preservation, vitality and viability of cities, especially cities that pursue regenerative pathways. Urban development and regeneration planning will aspire to provide strategic growth through restoration and reparation of degraded and damaged SES rather than just maintaining the status quo or going back to a previous stable state. The future is so much bigger than the past and even the present; and with an increasing number of people on the earth and in our

Table 3 Regenerative Citywide Inclusive Sanitation

Key Concepts	Regenerative Urban Development	Regenerative Sanitation	Integration and Systemic Operations	Possible Outcomes
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Regenerate and Sustain ✓ Repair and Restore ✓ Reduced Ecological Footprints ✓ Biophilia and Biomimicry ✓ Urban Resilience and Adaptability ✓ Resource Efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Treat and Reuse ✓ Restore and Repair ✓ Rehabilitate and/or Decommission ✓ Renewable energy and materials ✓ Organic Fertilizers ✓ Sanitation Ecological Infrastructure ✓ Design for Nature ✓ No-transfer-of-burden 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Reuse treated water for agriculture, husbandry and groundwater recharge ✓ Reuse of treated water to create and enhance greenfields (grazing areas)/landscapes, wetlands, aquatic habitats, forests and tree planting ✓ Reuse of water in industrial and construction applications ✓ Reuse of organic matter as fertilizer in agriculture and feed in husbandry and aquaculture ✓ Biogas for domestic use ✓ Bioenergy to power municipal facilities like street lights, community parks/halls, schools, etc ✓ Reuse treated water and materials to regenerate damaged ecosystem ✓ Harvesting resources from high density buildings and neighborhoods for reuse within the same vicinity ✓ Delineate the urban area into sani-sheds (perhaps using wards) for decentralized management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Sanitation-water-energy nexus ✓ Municipal Comprehensive and Integrated Treatment and Resource Recovery facility ✓ Food sufficiency ✓ Ecosystem conservation ✓ Carbon sequestration ✓ Reduced Ecological Footprints ✓ Specific technology for coastal areas and water-scarce areas ✓ Contextual sanitation systems depending on features of areas within the urban SES
	<i>Beyond Sustainability</i>			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Place and People Centered ✓ Self-reliance and Internalization ✓ Urban-Rural Linkages ✓ Compactness ✓ Ecological Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Social-Ecological-System Management ✓ Hybridized Technological Solutions ✓ Resilient and Functional Facilities ✓ Place and Scale Planning ✓ Appropriate Technological System Management ✓ Design for the base-of-the-pyramid ✓ Psycho-socio-eco-philta 		
	<i>Context-specific and Density</i>			
	<i>Systemic & Adaptive Governance & Management</i>			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Participatory Management ✓ Collaborative Governance ✓ Regenerative Standards and Codes ✓ Local Resource Management ✓ Communicative Rationale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Systemic Holistic Integration ✓ Participation and Partnership ✓ Standardization ✓ Emergency Sanitation Response Management ✓ Sanitation Market ✓ Integrated Hybrid Management System ✓ Blended Financing ✓ Multilevel Actors ✓ Fit-for-purpose governance ✓ Target Policies and Institutions 		

<i>Circular Urban Metabolism</i>				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Closed Consumption and Production Cycle ✓ Integrated Urban Ecological Infrastructure and Service System ✓ Renewable Materials ✓ Reuse and Recycle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Closed-Cycle Resource System Management ✓ Recovery, Recycling and Safe Reuse ✓ Sanitation Resource Management ✓ Design for Products and Services ✓ Design for recovery and Reuse 		
<i>Citizen's Quality of Life</i>				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Neighborhood Cohesion ✓ Close Proximity ✓ Enhanced Public Spaces ✓ Equitable Knowledge-sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Population at the base-of-the-pyramid ✓ Sani-shed management ✓ Available information and clear communication 		
<i>Local Economy</i>				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ New Circular Economy ✓ Livelihood Support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Integrated Functional Sanitation Service Chain ✓ Upskilling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Create sanitation market for goods and services ✓ Enable exchange of resources between different producers and service providers ✓ Recognition of the Sanitation profession (formal and informal) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Sanitation Economy ✓ Sanitation Entreprises and Entrepreneurs ✓ New Job Levels and Categories ✓ Reduced movement of materials ✓ Reduced ecological footprint
<i>Research & Development</i>				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Systemic Interconnections of urban infrastructure ✓ Systemic integration of operations and management for urban infrastructure and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ North and South ✓ Hybridized Solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Multidisciplinary ✓ Transdisciplinary ✓ Systemic Centralized and Decentralized Management ✓ Local Governance And Management 	

1 **Table 4 Elements of Regenerative Citywide Inclusive Sanitation**

<i>Governance and management</i>	<i>Infrastructure development and Service delivery management</i>	<i>Recovery, recycling and reuse</i>	<i>Partnerships and Participation</i>	<i>Local economy, enterprises and employment</i>
Context-specific multi-level and collaborative governance system (policies, institutions, mandates, regulations, etc)	Context-specific hybrid, resilient and nature-based solutions	Crop farms	Business-Business	Integrated functional sanitation value chain (IFSVC)
Local government/municipal management and agencies	Integrated risk assessment and hazard analysis	Animal farms	Business-Municipality	Taxes and revenues
Citizen Involvement National/state legal framework, and blended financing	Operations and maintenance	Fish farms	Business-Citizens	Blended financing
Systemic-holistic outlook	Symbiotic and systemic operations (circular metabolism)	Domestic cooking and Home gardens	Citizen-Municipality	Sanitation economy
Emergency response management (prevention, preparedness, adaptation and mitigation)	Affordability and willingness to pay	Public transport fuel and Municipal energy use for schools, community halls, markets, etc	Development-Partners-Donors-Citizens-Business	Sanitation enterprises and entrepreneurs
Participatory management	Co-management and service delivery	Green spaces landscape and grazing area	Citizen-resident-stakeholders participation	Sanitation professionals and workers
Quality requirements and standardization	Monitoring and evaluation/Quality standards		Nature and man	Sanitation exports
Ecosystem and natural resource management	Sanitation service chain design			
	Urban ecological infrastructure system			
	Santi-shed and neighbourhood delineation			
	Density and compactness			
Informal settlements and the population at the base-of-the-pyramid (BoPs)				
Municipal Comprehensive resource recovery and reuse factory				
Research-Innovation-Practice (RIP) Transdisciplinary, cross-collaborations, multi-perspectives, theoretical foundations				

2
3
4

Figure 1 Regenerative Citywide Inclusive Sanitation (Reg-CWIS) within specific SES

cities, demands will be exponentially high and the impact on urban society and ecosystem will be unprecedented. Doing things the same way may not be effective because tomorrow is nothing like we have seen or imagined. This is so true of sanitation and the correct fragile state of cities' management of the by-products-of-human-digestion and other related issues. Therefore, a regenerative pathway to urban sanitation should be crucial to city planners and managers; and then coordinated to manage and prevent sanitation-related crisis or disaster in a circular metabolic flow with particular emphasis on food, water, energy, ecosystem and economy. This will require regenerative worldviews and principles and certain key considerations for the systemic-integration of sanitation into urban development. This paper presents a regenerative pathway for CWIS (Figure 1), which consists of five levels and five components with 32 considerations (there could be more).

- I. *Strategic Planning for Urban SES*: The importance of strategic thinking and planning for regenerative cities cannot be over-emphasised. And one major challenging barrier to sanitation coverage, particularly in low and middle-income countries is mismatched governance structures and operations. It was suggested that for long-term sustainability of sanitation infrastructure and services, government support, legal and regulatory frameworks, institutional arrangements, skills and capacities, financial arrangements, and socio-cultural acceptance must be highly considered in any planning pathway (Luthi and Narayan 2018, CWIS 2018, Hawkins et al 2013, Reymond et al 2016, Luthi et al 2011b, Luthi, Markard and Parkinson 2011c). A weak public sector with fragmented and overlapping governance structures is often a recipe for poor planning, management and uncoordinated actions, and even resource and influence conflicts (Reymond et al 2016, Tilley and Dodane, 2014, Bassan 2014). Other key challenges are the silo short-term and techno-focused approaches to urban sanitation planning as well as financial constraints, which have often led to failure in sanitation management in the past (Luthi and Narayan 2018, CWIS 2018, Reymond et al 2016, Girardet et al 2014, Woo et al 2014). Therefore, the formulation of a comprehensive, long-term, systemic, inclusive and multiscale/level plan that is interwoven into the entire fabric of the city's development plans through multilevel and decentralized governance (Luthi and Narayan 2018, CWIS 2018, Reymond et al 2016, Girardet et al 2017, 2014, Kennedy et al 2011, Luthi et al 2011a(book), Girardet 2010) is paramount. This Plan should consider barriers to sanitation analysis, integrated risk assessment, resource potential and inclusiveness. Also, in order to capture a broad picture and build a standard broad and flexible platform, the process needs to be multi- (trans-) disciplinary with multi-stakeholder consultations and cross-collaborations. A systemic-integrated outlook and a circular (rather than linear) consideration for operations and management as well as material flows will give room for integrated management and resource harnessing and reuse (Kootatp et al 2019, CWIS 2018, Luthi and Narayan 2018, Editorial 2018, Scott et al 2017, Li et al 2017, Pandit et al 2017, Andersson et al 2016a, Reymond et al 2016, Girardet et al 2017, 2014, Kennedy et al 2011, Luthi et al 2011a(book), Girardet 2010). Circular rather than linear thinking will support resource governance perspectives that offer up opportunities to contribute to economic, social and environment goals of cities by tapping into the resource recovery and reuse potentials inherent in sanitation to generate added value to society and still protect the all-round urban SES Anderson et al 2016). Emergency response management should also be part of the plan to protect the resilience of the city through preparedness, prevention and mitigation (Cookey and Peter-Cookey 2019). ReGenSan must be centrally integrated within RUD and such holistic frameworks can break barriers that traditionally confine sanitation infrastructure, service delivery, perceptions and perspectives (Andersson et al 2016a). This is the very first step to any Reg-CWIS as the world races towards 2030.
- II. *Systemic and Integrated Structures*: The dynamic complexities of cities' SES require more integrated, effective, functional, reliable services with comprehensive, place-based and multi-scalar infrastructures (Li et al 2017) that allow regeneration through symbiotic operational interactions that could ensure resilience, functionality, reliability and resourcefulness of the urban system (Girardet et al 2017, Li et al 2017, Pandit et al 2017, Chand 2017, Roggema 2017, Ma et al 2015). Thus, context-specific symbiotic and hybrid infrastructure and services will enable regenerative cities provide functional, effective and reliable services with efficient and well-maintained infrastructure that harness the inherent resources in sanitation-derived-resources. When cities

implement systemic and integrated infrastructure and services systems, they reap benefits in cost, water, energy and food efficiency as well as ecosystem preservation and enhanced resilience (Kootattep et al 2019, Cooney and Peter-Cookey 2019, Pandit et al 2017, Li et al 2017, Ma et al 2015, Perales-Mompaler et al 2015, Luthi et al 2011, Reymond et al 2009). The 'synergistic and symbiotic interactions' of material flows between components of an urban infrastructure system (i.e. infrastructural symbiosis) and the SES of the city-region (i.e. infrastructure ecology) could result in lower ecological footprints (Pandit et al 2017). Primarily, it could entail the systematic integration of infrastructure to maximize the intake and reuse of resource (e.g. water, energy and nutrients) flowing interchangeably to deliver service at different levels (Ma et al 2015, Pandit et al 2017) – for instance a sewage treatment plant can extract the biogas needed for its own processes. Highly and densely populated cities will produce large and concentrated volumes of sanitation matter and so a system that incorporates harnessing the inherent resources need to evaluate the related energy values for its structures to operate at optimum efficiency (Ma et al 2015) and make the best of the interconnections between the subsystems of the SES (Kootattep et al 2019). For this route will require considerations such as context-specific hybrid infrastructure and services (which could combine sewer and non-sewer, centralized and decentralized, household and neighborhood, etc) and technology-design and development (e.g. in piping, collection, storage, treatment, recovery, reuse, etc), urban ecological infrastructural symbiosis (e.g. connecting infrastructure to work with nature such as wetlands, etc), symbiotic infrastructure and services (e.g. capturing energy and nutrients to feed inter or intra elements connected to each other – like the municipal organic waste recovery facility in Lille, France that provides compost for the agricultural areas and also fuel for over 100 public buses, thereby reducing the use of five million gallons (Brown 2014, in Pandit et al 2017) and the low-cost hybrid power plant and distribution network in India and Tanzania (HUSK 2018), symbiotic infrastructure and services (e.g. wastewater could be treated at neighborhood levels for maximum energy and nutrient recovery to support energy supply for residential and office buildings and organic fertilizer for urban and peri-urban agriculture and home gardening (Ma et al 2015, Woo et al 2014, Lazarus 2009). All of these make resource recovery and reuse an essential consideration when determining infrastructure ecology and service delivery.

- III. *Operations and Management*: The quality of the operations and management of these symbiotic infrastructure and service delivery system will depend on pre-determined aims and goals based on regenerative worldviews and principles. This will be achieved through collaborative, local and nexus management with specific technical quality and operational standards. Co-management (local governments, businesses, civil society and citizens/residents) and mutual beneficial processes with nexus cycles (of sanitation-water-solid waste-energy-food-ecosystem-economy and sanitation- health-wellbeing-education-livelihood-economy -- see Figure 3) will not only reduce costs and wastage, but provide holistic citywide solutions and revenue from the sales of sanitation-derive-products like bioenergy, organic matter, nutrients and treated water (Metson et al 2018, Poorvliet et al 2018, Daudey 2018, Scott et al 2017, Chand 2017, Andersson et al 2016a,b, Reymond et al 2016, Persson et al 2015, Dagerskog et al 2014, Anand and Anul 2014, Luthi et al 2011a, Seidu 2010, Weiland 2010); and then taxes of enterprises, professionals, workers and exports of businesses that such supplies support. To move on this regenerative path will require considerations such as local, decentralized and collaborative management structures that combine different operations and service delivery, possibly, under the same agency and management, which could also run a municipality multi-recovery and recycling facility that provides SDPs for the reuse market at different levels (household, neighborhood, sani-sheds, industry, businesses, etc) as in Lille, France (see Figure 2). Sanitation-derived products (SDPs) could be reused as organic fertilizer in agriculture, animal feed in aquaculture and animal husbandry, fertilizer and soil conditioner in horticulture, home gardening, landscaping, grazing land and reforestation, ecosystem services for constructed wetlands and aquatic restoration, treated water for industrial and domestic uses, biogas generation and biomass production for domestic and community energy supply, even construction materials (Andersson et al 2016a,b, Kootattep et al 2019). This could earnestly boost local enterprises and economy and also provide new businesses and jobs for the city's residents, which could extend beyond urban boundaries and also to hinterlands. It also contributes to enhancing resilience, water and energy efficiency, food sufficiency and reducing ecological footprints. In

Kampala, Uganda, it was estimated that reusing sewage sludge and organic solid waste as combustion fuel could replace almost all the city's consumption of firewood (Andersson et al 2016, Ddiba 2016), and this is good news for the fight against increasing carbon emissions and deforestation. The sanitation-water-energy-health-education-wellbeing nexus when woven into the intricate lines of the whole system will ensure public and environmental health, protection, information and communication and quality of life of urban dwellers. The decentralized and collaborative management structure also allows for interactive decision-making and operations/maintenance between the local governments, city residents, civil society, business and industry, academia and research, and then the hinterlands (far and near) (Kootattep et al 2019, Axinte et al 2019, Andersson et al 2016a, Scott et al 2017, Poortvliet et al 2018, Reymond et al 2016, Hawkins et al 2013, Luthi et al 2011a, Girardet et al 2017, 2014, Kennedy et al 2011). Furthermore, neighborhood and sani-shed management will encourage stakeholder involvement, shared-costs, reduce material and financial costs, and encourage reuse at neighborhood and household levels so that there is less to be transported out. In fact, a Dutch survey conducted by researchers in the Wageningen University (Netherlands) found out that 64 percent of respondents were open to new sanitation such as reuse of SDPs (Poortvliet et al 2018). For example, the multiple award-winning BedZed facility in the United Kingdom (UK) captured and treated sanitation matter at building levels and used them to maintain sky gardens within the eco-designed buildings (Lazarus 2015) as is also practiced in Singapore (Woo et al 2014, Luthi et al 2011a). In addition, a municipality center could collect resources from sani-shed treatment and recovery facilities that are fed from neighborhood points which were in turn fed from proximal households and other connected buildings and spaces (see Figure 3). The resources derived from the sani-shed facilities could then be further processed in the central municipal facility and then distributed to areas and markets where they are needed within and beyond the urban system. This will give birth to sanitation entrepreneurs, enterprises, professional and workers at different levels and categories, which will also go on to drive an urban inter/intra sanitation market across sani-sheds and more to build a local sanitation economy way bigger than the sanitation-service-chain (SSC) and ultimately boost local economic development and citizen livelihood/wellbeing (Andersson et al 2016a).

- IV. *Research, Innovation and Practice (RIP)*: The road to regenerative urban development can be an arduous challenge and complicated endeavor that is unavoidable. As difficult as that is, though, adding urban sanitation to the twist makes it a 'wicked challenge' (UNDP 2016, Rittel and Webber 1973, Hawkins et al 2013). But, it must happen for the benefit of man and nature in a way that builds an equilibrium existence between city residents, the surrounding ecosystems and natural resources, economic growth and livelihood support, resilience and sustainability, as well as keeping the global interconnections healthy. This complex and confusing maze needs multi-layered solutions in research and practice if the aspirations of the SDGs will be realized by 2030. It has been pointed out that sanitation has a strong connection, impact and influence on all the SDGs (Susana 2018) and mostly SDG 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 11 and 12 (Andersson et al 2016a, Reymond et al 2016). The dynamic complexities of cities' SES and the eclectic expectations across race, ethnicities, age, gender, personal preferences, culture, occupation, status, industry, politics, and so on, indicate that silo approaches and exclusive perspectives only make things worse. It is, therefore, important that research shifts from mono-perspectives, methods and disciplines to cross and multi-foci approaches that see from several lenses and user perceptions, and also work from several angles to create and develop octopi-solutions for technology, infrastructure and practice of Reg-CWIS. People need to be at the center of sanitation innovations and research to be effective and acceptable. This is one of the few criticisms of the faecal sludge management framework (FSM), commonly used in sanitation research and practice, that focuses on technology, logistics whilst giving little attention to user preferences, behaviors and decisions that are fundamental to effective and successful sanitation management. In addition, the intentional simplified and linear direction that fails to capture the inherent complexities of managing sanitation in today's global cities (Scott et al 2017). Another issue is the fact that households bear the costs of faecal sludge management (FSM) systems are often borne more by households unlike when utilities bear the costs more with sewer systems, which is probably based on the fact that users have to pay for installation, construction, maintenance, desludging, etc (Daudey 2018). As a matter of fact, determining the costs and comprehensive

societal values of SDPs such as biogas, fertilizers, treated water and nutrients and other organic matter will require integrated analysis. In Spain and Italy, for example, reuse of treated wastewater (using a treatment and constructed wetland respectively) in place of irrigation water and chemical fertilizer resulted in cost savings, improved ecosystem health and services (Andersson et al 2016a, Verlicchi et al 2012, Heinz et al 2011) and don't forget the reduction in firewood benefits in Uganda. It is expedient to consider costs and recognize and engage users in decision-making, research, innovations and practice as they contribute hugely to the success of any CiWISIS. Research is key to the future of cities and their sanitation platforms. The kind of innovations that go beyond sustainability to think outside-the-box of toilet and technology to working with nature and around peculiar social and ecological/geographical features (e.g. wetlands). Additionally, resource-constrained innovations that are affordable, of good quality and effective need to be considered for the BoPs without undermining the advanced innovations for the affluent, unique and/or adventurous (Zeschky et al 2014). It is also pertinent to note that research investigations should be based on multi-theoretical lenses and comprehensive conceptual frameworks while practice and implementation should be cross-collaborative in disciplines, professions and agencies. This will encourage interwoven innovative solutions that cover myriad aspects of the challenges face in urban sanitation and city management. For example, the Research Triangle Institute (RTI) innovation that include a toilet with onsite treatment facility, which is designed to treat and reuse solid and liquid waste to generate combustive energy and use this to electrochemically disinfect liquid waste and convert by-products of human digestion into stored energy and burnable fuel. This is being tested in Durban (South Africa) and Ahmedabad (India) (Morrison et al 2018, RTI 2017). Also, in India and Tanzania, a hybrid power plant and distribution network operates by combining and synchronizing solar, biomass and batteries to deliver reliable 24/7 power on a pay-as-you-go basis with a mobile-enable smart metering system to support local businesses, improve citizen's quality of life and reduce carbon footprints (HUSK 2018). In addition, Reymond et al (2016) suggest looking at synergies between different services like energy, multi-functional operations and the valorisations of SDPs, which should all be backed by policy and citizen support (Luthi and Narayan 2018, Woo et al 2014, Girardet et al 2014, Luthi et al 2011a, 2009). Composting and urine diversion toilets (e.g. Blue Diversion Toilet) can be considered for water-scarce and hard-to-reach areas (Kootatp et al 2019, Tobias et al 2017, Anand and Anul 2014). RIP cannot be effective and practical without users' involvement that captures the reality and bird-eye view of the challenge.

- V. *Expected Outcomes*: This regenerative pathway to CWIS should aim for directed and targeted outcomes because they will, in a roundabout way affect the process and implementation of the plan. Thus, some key expectations should include formal and official marriage of ReGenSan with RUD as frameworks for planning sanitation management or urban (re)development of any city. Focus should also see a future that creates and sustains sanitation entrepreneurs, enterprises, professionals and workers as well as sanitation markets and exports, which all lead to a robust sanitation economy. All of these should be combine with aspiring for effective, functional and safe services, practice and use, including protection and prevention mechanisms to support and boost the city's resilience and recoverability. Essentially, all of these (and indeed the entire journey) is dependent on strong, comprehensive and collaborative governance and management from policies, institutions, regulations and citizen participation.

Figure 3 Potential for collection, recovery, recycling and reuse of sanitation-derived-products at neighbourhood and sani-shed levels

3.0 DISCUSSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The future of the world's cities could be really jeopardized if a proper handle is not designed for sanitation within the urban development agenda, which operates away from the techno-separatist paradigm that relegates it to the bottom of the list of priorities or shrouded under the shadow of great concerns like water, health and environment. The faeco-phobia culture also needs to be addressed along with misconceptions of the resource-potential of sanitation products; and then sanitation infrastructure and service delivery need to be conceptualized in a contextual, systemic, holistic and integrated manner that links the entire system and process to the lifeblood of the city in order to contribute to food security, carbon sequestration, energy supply, horticulture, ecological sustainability and ensuring the aesthetic quality of the environment and public places in such a way that captures the psycho-socio-cultural-economic factors, governance and institutional framework, geographical and ecological features, territorial boundaries and stakeholders of the urban system (Luthi et al. 2009, van Vliet et al. 2011, Luthi and McConville 2011, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013, Brands 2014, Reymond et al. 2016, Koottatep et al. 2019).

UD and UR discussions often centred on the astonishing dynamic infrastructural and technical complexities without really considering the fact that more people engage in considerable toilet and hygiene activities daily and these have direct and indirect impacts on urban living and ecosystems as a whole, which threatens resilience and sustainability (Parkinson et al. 2009, Lehman 2010a/b, Jewitt 2011, Anastasiadis and Metaxas 2013, Czisk et al. 2015, Koottatep et al. 2019). Often times, decision-makers and other stakeholders avoid the unsavoury discussions of faeces and urine management preferring to hide them as water and wastewater issues and this derails the SDG 11 targets for inclusive, safe and resilient cities (Bai et al 2016, UNDP 2016, Schmidt et al. 2017, Koottatep et al. 2019). And, in spite of the persistent gospel of sustainable urban sanitation (SUS), urban planning decision-makers and city residents have consistently pursued unsustainable solutions (Luthi et al. 2009, Andersson et al. 2016, Reymond et al. 2016) that often do not fit into the governance and contextual features of their urban system. It is, therefore, of great essence that in the race towards 2030, ReGenSan solutions are integrated into RUD strategies to yield increased efficiency and effectiveness, reduced costs and risks, upgraded livelihoods, preserved public health and natural ecosystem, food, water and energy security and infrastructural integrity, ecological sustainability as well as an accelerated drive towards expanded access and improved services (Luthi et al. 2009, Andersson et al. 2016, Reymond et al. 2016, Koottatep et al. 2019).

The CWIS holistic and incremental approach is a precursor to the focus of this paper, which actively steers urban sanitation and development debates towards mutual interactions that focus on co-related outcomes and not isolatory conditions. Also, targeting environmental considerations, nature-based and process-oriented solutions within cross-sectoral/levels partnerships are indicative of the regenerative paradigm (CWIS 2018, Luthi and Narayan, Parkinson, Luthi and Walther 2014). Successful regenerative cities of the 2030 SDG 11 aspirations must ensure safe sanitation management and this will require practical, realizable and progressive solutions that are co-managed and regulated from local government and municipal levels backed by multi-level governance frameworks with public-private-partnerships overseen by a dedicated unit within a comprehensive municipal agency. The SDG and NUA cities of 2030 and beyond should be able to also guarantee every resident and visitor non-discriminatory safe sanitation services at all times as part of standard quality of living and reduced potential for sanitation crisis and/or impacts from disaster events. Therefore, city managers and urban developers (particularly in developing countries) must work together with sanitation professionals and all other stakeholders in the overall conceptualization and planning of urban regeneration/development processes.

Building livable cities around a circular economy that pursues after reduced waste, resource recycling, natural systems adaptation, biophilic designs and plans, alternative energy and emission controls (Beatley 2005, 2012a,b, 2015, 2010, Beatley and Newman 2013, Lehman 2010a,b,c) will require cost-effective ways to recover, transform and reuse sanitation resources. Otherwise, the laudable objectives of the SDG 6 and 11 may be constrained due to the unconscious disregard of core urban sanitation in planning and design (e.g. sewer blockages and leakages, blackwater and sludge overflow into surface and ground water, foul odours and ugly sight of exposed excreta, health costs and mortality, and the loss of revenue from sanitation-derived-products); just as it could also benefit from incorporating safely managed sanitation in the world's cities (to protect public health, environmental quality, reduce attendant costs, etc), improve sanitation service delivery (e.g. emptying, collection, storage, transportation,

treatment/disposal), upgrade designs and development of sanitation devices and facilities (i.e. fabrication, construction, installation and connections of toilets, sewers, septic tanks, etc), provide organic resources for horticulture, urban greenery/landscapes, food (crop and animal) production, building materials and energy, support and protect natural systems, ensure sustainable governance and economy through instruments that engender the reuse of sanitation products and strengthen a sanitation economy within the city. It becomes expedient for urban planning and built environment professionals to work with sanitation professionals to embed core sanitation expectations towards inspiring effective and practical situations for the world's cities that do not negate the objectives of green urbanism and urban regeneration (as could be seen in cities of developing countries where streets are laden with sanitation matter and related disease burden is high). It is important to keep in mind the following elements:

- I. Sanitation is critical in urban planning as city residents will always actively perform the related physiological activities several times a day. Therefore, failing to plan for sanitation management from the initial stage or as a major objective may hinder progress or even ruin success.
- II. Sanitation resources contribute to cities as sanitation-derived-products and could be used in home-gardens, green roofs and walls, grazing areas, city parks and other greeneries, flower and plant shops, farms (crop/animal), building construction, cooking, lighting homes and municipal administrative buildings, powering essential facilities (e.g. schools, health centres, community halls, etc), stadia, markets, cinemas, etc.
- III. Resource recovery and reuse through recycling/upcycling and product transformation will reduce the costs of disposal as well as the volume of waste disposed; and thereby protect the environment and public health by reducing human contact (e.g. less hospitalizations, disease burden and ecosystem contamination) which also enhances the aesthetics of the city.
- IV. Energy recovery and reuse will provide renewable energy for use at varying degrees and result in energy conservation which could positively impact carbon emissions and climate change and reduce the city's ecological footprint.
- V. With appropriate technology designs, cities can have sanitation systems that fit their urban development plans and unique peculiarities and contexts (coastal, arid, mountain, densely-populated, luxury, industrial, etc) and with long-term systemic integrated planning and innovative solutions embedded with resource recovery and reuse options as well as sanitation emergency response and management could be incorporated into city master plans from initiation.
- VI. With systemic, holistic and integrating sanitation planning and management, cities can make the best use of land space, natural systems (e.g. wetlands, groundwater recharge, surface water nutrient for aquaculture, etc), transportation and conveyance routes for sanitation material, robust marketplace, etc.
- VII. The population at the base-of-the-pyramid (BoPs) in developing countries, who mostly live in poorer informal settlements that are often too densely populated and ill-planned could be included in city (re)development's sanitation plans, which should incorporate the homeless as well.
- VIII. Failed, unimproved, dysfunctional and abandoned sanitation facilities can be retrofitted, rehabilitated, repaired and/or the space recovered for proper use while new facilities could be appropriately sited.
- IX. The integrated functional sanitation value chain could create entrepreneurs, enterprises, employees and business networks that support the sanitation economy that in turn feeds the city's overall economy through taxes and revenues, not to mention, exports.
- X. A structured focused and integrated governance and management system will provide the enabling environment that ensures operations and service goals aiming not just for the SDG 6/11 targets, but also SDG 2, 3, 4, 7, 8 and 12 (SUSANA 2017); such as reduced ecological footprints through zero waste/emissions, energy recovery/reuse, food security, public/environmental quality and so on.
- XI. ReGenSan will provide architects, engineers, planners, policy-makers and city dwellers with fodder to determine the particular sanitation devices, facilities and infrastructural system required to benefit the overall city expectations and green urbanism designs.
- XII. Special financing mechanisms could support innovation and upscale of sanitation products and services as well as infrastructural developments within the city.

- XIII. Dense and compact cities are more sustainable and livable areas that could reduce urban sprawl to protect ecological systems, green spaces and agricultural land, but they could also lead to unhealthy and intolerable sanitary conditions that sicken residents (e.g. Kowloon Walled City, Hong Kong-Lehmann 2016) due to poor management and planning, which tend to crowded spaces and tight developments that make sanitation service delivery really difficult. There sani-shed management would be a viable option with hybridized solutions depending on accessibility and density. Sani-sheds could be delineated according to electoral wards (as prescribed by the laws of the land) or based on population (e.g. 10,000-50,000 residents or 70-120 dwelling units per hectare-Lehmann 2016). Population may be the best option since volume of faecal matter produced is a considerable concern. This will, of course, require proper policy and institutional backing in order to support continuity beyond political tenures.
- XIV. Multi-level governance and local management
- XV. Research and development

This may seem too idealistic and ambitious (as much of the world's ingenious concepts of today were once described), but with much study and practice, cities can find the equilibrium that fit. It would, however, require careful, appropriate and thoughtful well-researched governance and standardization.

REFERENCE

- Ahmadi, M., Cherqui, F., Aubin, J.B., and Le Gauffre, P., (2015): Sewer asset management: impact of sample size and its characteristics on the calibration outcomes of a decision-making multivariate model, *Urban Water Journal*, DOI: 10.1080/1573062X.2015.1011668
- Anastasiadis, P., and Metaxas, G., (2013) Formulating the principles of an eco – city. *World Transactions on Engineering and Technology Education* 11, (4) 394-399. [http://www.wiete.com.au/journals/WTE&TE/Pages/Vol.11.%20No.4%20\(2013\)/07-Metaxas-G.pdf](http://www.wiete.com.au/journals/WTE&TE/Pages/Vol.11.%20No.4%20(2013)/07-Metaxas-G.pdf) (accessed 29/06/2018)
- Andersson, K., Dickin, S., and Rosemarin, A., (2016) Towards “Sustainable” Sanitation: Challenges and Opportunities in Urban Areas. *Sustainability* 8, 1289; doi:10.3390/su8121289
- Ashley, R., and Hopkinson, P., (2002) Sewer systems and performance indicators—into the 21st century. *Urban Water* 4, 123–135. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1462-0758\(02\)00010-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1462-0758(02)00010-9)
- Banerjee, G., (2011) Underground pollution travel from leach pits of on-site sanitation facilities: A case study. *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy*, 13, 489–497
- Bai, X., Surveyer, A., Elmqvist, T., Gatzweiler, F.W., Guneralp, B., Parnell, S., Prieur-Richard, A., Shrivastava, P., Siri, J.G., Stafford-Smith, M., Toussaint, J., and Webb, R., (2016) Defining and advancing a systems approach for sustainable cities. *Environmental Sustainability* 23, 69–78. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2016.11.010>
- Beatley, T., 2005. *Native to Nowhere: sustaining home and community in a global age*. Island Press.
- Beatley, T., 2010. *Biophilic cities: integrating nature into urban design and planning*.
- Beatley, T., 2010 and Newman, P., 2013. Biophilic cities are sustainable, resilient cities. *Sustainability Journal*, 5, 3328-3345 (MDPI).
- Beatley, T., 2012a. *Green Urbanism: learning from European cities*. Island Press.
- Beatley, T., 2012b. *Green cities of Europe: global lessons on green urbanism*. Island Press.
- Beatley, T., 2015. *Planning for sustainability in European cities: a review of practice in leading cities*. The City Reader, ed. Richard T. LeGates and Frederic
- Bocken, N.M.P., Short, S.W., Rana, P., and Evans, S., (2014) A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 65, 42-56
- Brewerton, P., and Millward, L., (2001) *Organisational research methods*. London: Sage.
- Brown and Caldwell (1984) *Utility infrastructure rehabilitation*. NTIS No. PB86-N14642, U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development, Office of Policy Development and Research, Building Technology Division.
- Campbell, O.M. R., Benova, L., Gon, G., Afsana, K., and Cumming, O., (2015) Getting the basic rights – the role of water, sanitation and hygiene in maternal and reproductive health: a conceptual framework. *Tropical Medicine and International Health*, 20 (3) 252–267. doi:10.1111/tmi.12439
- Cairncross, S., Bartram, J., Cumming, O., and Brocklehurst, C., (2010) Hygiene, Sanitation, and Water: What Needs to Be Done? *PLoS Med* 7(11): e1000365. doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1000365. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2981587/pdf/pmed.1000365.pdf> (accessed 18/03/2019)
- Cookey, P. E. (2013) *Public Health Risk Assessment of Decentralized Wastewater Treatment Systems in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria*. A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Science in Environmental Engineering and Management with area of Specialization in Environmental Technology for Sustainable Development at the Asian Institute of Technology, Bangkok and the degree of Master of Science at the UNESCO-IHE, Delft, The Netherlands.
- Cookey, P. E., Koottatep, T., van der Steen, P., and Lens, P. N. L., (2016a) Public health risk assessment tool: strategy to improve public policy framework for onsite wastewater treatment systems (OWTS). *Journal of Water, Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, 06.1, 74-88. doi: 10.2166/washdev.2016.081.

- Cookey, P. E., Darnasawadi, R., and Ratanachai, C., (2016b) A Conceptual Framework for Assessment of Governance Performance of Lake Basins: *Towards Transformation to Adaptive and Integrative Governance*. *Hydrology* 2016, 3(1), 12; doi:[10.3390/hydrology3010012](https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrology3010012)
- Corcoran, E., C. Nellemann, E. Baker, R. Bos, D. Osborn, H. Savelli (eds.), (2010) Sick Water? The central role of wastewater management in sustainable development. A Rapid Response Assessment. United Nations Environment Programme, UN-HABITAT, GRID-Arendal. www.grida.no ISBN: 978-82-7701-075-5. https://gridarendal-website-live.s3.amazonaws.com/production/documents/:s_document/208/original/SickWater_sc_reen.pdf?1486721310 (accessed 23/03/2018).
- CSIR (Council for Scientific and Industrial Research), (2007). "Spot check assessments of MIG water and sanitation projects." <http://www.dwaf.gov.za/Masibambane/documents/monitoring-evaluation/MIGSpotcheckApr07part1.pdf> (Jun. 4, 2013).
- Czischke, D., Moloney, C., and Turcu, C., (2015) State of the Art on Sustainable regeneration in urban areas, URBACT II capitalization. Published by URBACT, Saint Denis, France. http://urbact.eu/sites/default/files/soa_04-final-03.pdf (accessed 29/06/2018)
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2012). Towards the Circular Economy: Opportunities for the consumer goods sector, Vol. 1. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/publications/Ellen-MacArthur-Foundation-Towards-the-Circular-Economy-vol.1.pdf> (accessed 07/09/2017).
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2013). Towards the Circular Economy: Opportunities for the consumer goods sector, Vol. 2. https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/publications/TCE_Report-2013.pdf (accessed 07/09/2017).
- El-Sheikh, M. A., (2011) Optimization and upgrading wastewater treatment plants. *Journal of Engineering Sciences*, Assiut University, 39, (4), 697-713. http://www.aun.edu.eg/journal_files/82_J_8366.pdf (accessed 30/04/2017)
- EMF 2015. Towards a circular economy: business rationale for an accelerated transition. Ellen MacArthur Foundation.
- EMF 2017. Cities in the circular economy: an initial exploration.
- Esrey, S. A., (2001) Towards a recycling society ecological sanitation – closing the loop to food security. *Water Sci Technol.* 43 (4), 177-87
- Fam, D. M. and Mitchell, C. A., (2012) Sustainable innovation in wastewater management: lessons for nutrient recovery and reuse, *Local Environment: The International Journal of Justice and Sustainability*, DOI:10.1080/13549839.2012.716408
- Fenner, R. A., and Saward, G., (2004) Towards Assessing Sewer Performance and Serviceability Using Knowledge Based Systems. Ninth International Conference on Urban Drainage (9ICUD). <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/pdf/10.1061/40644%282002%2982> (accessed 06/04/2018)
- Fullerton, J., 2015. Regenerative Capitalism: how universal principles and patterns will shape our new economy.
- Galli, G., Nothomb, C., Baetings, E., 2014. Towards Systemic Change in Urban Sanitation. IRC Working Paper. IRC, The Hague.
- Jenkins, M.W., Cumming, O., Cairncross, S. (2015) Pit latrine emptying behavior and demand for sanitation services in Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 12, 2588–2611
- Kaminsky, J., and Javernick-Will, A., (2015) Theorizing the Internal Social Sustainability of Sanitation Organizations. DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0000933. *J. Constr. Eng. Manage.*, 141(2): 04014071
- Kemp, G., (2000) Sewerage assets, their condition and relationship to performance. Proceedings of IWA / IAHR / CIWEM Joint 1-day Conference on Performance Indicators for Urban Drainage, University of Hertfordshire, December 6, 2000.
- Koottatep, T., Cookey, P.E., and Polprasert, C., (2019) Regenerative Sanitation: A Framework for Sanitation 4.0. ISBN 1780409672, 9781780409672, IWA Publishing, the Netherlands https://books.google.com.ng/books/about/Regenerative_Sanitation.html?id=6MgstwEACAAJ&redir_esc=y&hl=en (accessed 29/06/2018)
- Kvarnström, E., McConville, J., Bracken, P., Johansson, M., and Fogde, M., (2011) "The Sanitation Ladder – a Need for a Revamp?" *Journal of Water Sanitation and Hygiene for Development*, vol. 1(1) 3- 12.
- Lehmann, S., (2010a) Green Urbanism: Formulating a Series of Holistic Principles », *S.A.P.I.EN.S* 3.2, <http://sapiens.revues.org/1057>,
- Lehman, S, 2010b. The principles of Green Urbanism: transforming the city for sustainability.
- Lehman, S, 2010c. The principles of Green Urbanism: the post-industrial city.
- Levy, Y., and Ellis, T.J., (2006). A systems approach to conduct an effective literature review in support of information systems research. *Informing Sci. J.* 9, 181-212
- Lopes, A. M., Fam, D., and Williams, J., (2012) Designing sustainable sanitation: Involving design in innovative, transdisciplinary research. *Design Studies* 33, 298-317. doi:10.1016/j.destud.2011.08.005
- Marshall, R. E., and Farahbakhsh, K., (2013) Systems approaches to integrated solid waste management in developing countries. *Waste Management* 33, 988–1003. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.12.023>
- Martínez-Jurado, P. J., and Moyano-Fuentes, J., (2014) Lean Management, Supply Chain Management and Sustainability: A Literature Review. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 85, 134-150
- Mayring, P., (2003) *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse – Grundlagen und Techniken*. [Qualitative content analysis]. 8th ed. Weinheim, Germany: Beltz Verlag.
- Miszta-Kruk, K., (2016) Reliability and failure rate analysis of pressure, vacuum and gravity sewer systems based on operating data. *Engineering Failure Analysis* 61, 37–45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engfailanal.2015.07.034>

- Murray A. and Buckley C. (2009). Designing reuse-oriented sanitation infrastructure: the design for service planning approach. In: Wastewater Irrigation and Health Assessing and Mitigating Risk in Low-income Countries, P. Drechsel, C. A. Scott, L. Raschid-Sally, M. Redwood and A. Bahri (eds), Earthscan, London, UK.
- Murray A. and Ray I. (2010). Commentary: back-end users: the unrecognized stakeholders in demand-driven sanitation. *Journal of Planning Education and Research*, OnlineFirst, published on May 6, 2010, doi: 10.1177/0739456X10369800
- Nassar, U., (2013) Principles of Green Urbanism: the Absent Value in Cairo, Egypt. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity* 3, (4) 339-343. <http://www.ijssh.org/papers/258-C00007.pdf> (accessed 18/03/2019)
- Novak, J., and Canas, A., (2008) The Theory Underlying Concept Maps and How to Construct and Use Them. Florida Institute for Human and Machine Cognition. Available at <http://cmap.ihmc.us/Publications/ResearchPapers/TheoryUnderlyingConceptMaps.pdf>.
- Nunes, D.M, Tome, A., and Pinheiro, D.M, (2013) Urban Regeneration - Developing strong sustainable urban design perspectives. Chapter 9 - Urban Regeneration, In: Portugal SB13 - Contribution of Sustainable Building to Meet EU 20-20-20 Targets. Edited by Luís Bragança Manuel Pinheiro Ricardo Mateus. ISBN 978-989-96543-7-2 https://www.irbnet.de/daten/iconda/CIB_DC26467.pdf (accessed 16/03/2019)
- Ostrom, E., (2005) Understanding institutional diversity. Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey, USA.
- Pahl-Wostl C., (2009) A conceptual framework for analysing adaptive capacity and multi-level learning processes in resource governance regimes. *Global Environmental Change* 19(3): 354-365. doi:10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2009.06.001
- Pahl-Wostl, C., Holtz, G., Kastens, B., and Knieper, C., (2010) Analyzing complex water governance regimes: the Management and Transition Framework. *environmental science & policy*, 13, 571–581
- Pahl-Wostl, C., Jeffrey, P., Isendahl, N., and Brugnach, M., (2011) Maturing the New Water Management Paradigm: Progressing from Aspiration to Practice. *Water Resour Manage* 25, 837–856. DOI 10.1007/s11269-010-9729-2
- Potter, A., Klutse, A., Snehaltha, M., Batchelor, C., Uandela, A., Naafs, A., Fonseca, C., and Moriarty, P., (2011) Assessing sanitation service levels. IRC International Water and Sanitation Centre, Working Paper 3 Second Edition. <https://www.ircwash.org/sites/default/files/Potter-2011-Assessing.pdf> (accessed 18/05/2017)
- Piana, V, 2010. Urban Regeneration. Economics Web Institute. <http://www.economicwebinstitute.org/glossary/urbanregeneration.htm>
- Prüss, A., Kay, D., Fewtrell, L., Bartram, J., others, 2002. Estimating the burden of disease from water, sanitation, and hygiene at a global level. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 110, 537-542.
- Qasem, A., Zayed, T., and Chen, Z., (2009) A Condition Rating System for Wastewater Treatment Plants Infrastructures. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Environmental and Ecological Engineering*, Vol:3, No:4. <https://waset.org/publications/15241/a-condition-rating-system-for-wastewater-treatment-plants-infrastructures> (accessed 23/03/2018)
- Reynolds, J. H., and Barrett, M. H., (2003) A review of the effects of sewer leakage on groundwater quality. *Water and Environment Journal*, 17 (11) 34-39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-6593.2003.tb00428.x>
- Rockefeller Foundation (2014) City Resilience Framework. <https://assets.rockefellerfoundation.org/app/uploads/20140410162455/City-Resilience-Framework-2015.pdf> (accessed 30/10/2019)
- Rodgers, A. F., Ajono, L. A., Gyapong, J. O., Hagan, M., and Emerson, P. M. (2007). “Characteristics of latrine promotion participants and non-participants; inspection of latrines; and perceptions of household latrines in northern Ghana.” *Trop. Med. Int. Health*, 12(6), 772–782.
- Schmitt, R.J.P., Morgenroth, E., and Larsen, T.A., (2017) Robust planning of sanitation services in urban informal settlements: An analytical framework. *Water Research* 110, 297-312. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.12.007>
- Sethi, V., and King, W. R., (1998) Organizational transformation thought business process reengineering. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Shivendra, B.T.; Ramaraju, H.K. (2015) Impact of Onsite Sanitation System on Groundwater in Different Geological Settings of Peri Urban Areas. *Aquat. Procedia*, 4, 1162–1172.
- Stout, 536-547. Taylor and Francis, Routeledge.
- Tucci, C., Goldenfum, J.A., and Parkinson J.N. (2009) “*Integrated Urban Water Management: Humid Tropics*” ISBN: 978-92-3-104065-8 CRC Press. p. 2. Retrieved 2009-09-18.
- UNDP, 2014. Human Development Report 2014: Sustaining Human Progress- Reducing Vulnerability and Building Resilience. United Nations Development Programme, New York.
- UNDP (2016) UNDP Support to the Implementation of the 2030 Agenda. UNPD
- UNDP (2006) Human Development Report 2006: Beyond Scarcity: Power, Poverty and the Global Water Crisis. Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke; New York.
- UNICEF/WHO (2015) United Nations Children's Fund/World Health Organization. Progress on Sanitation and Drinking Water: 2015 Update and MDG Assessment; UNICEF/WHO: New York, NY, USA, 2015.
- van Vliet, B.J.M, Spaargaren, G., and Oosterveer, P., (2011) Sanitation under challenge: contributions from the social sciences. *Water Policy* 13, 797-809.
- van Welie, M. J., and Romijn, H. A., (2018) NGOs fostering transitions towards sustainable urban sanitation in low income countries: Insights from Transition Management and Development Studies. *Environmental Science & Policy* 84, 250-260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2017.08.011>
- WHO/UNICEF (2017) washdata_Trends-in sanitation service levels (2000-2015) _20180629142634 <https://washdata.org/data#!/dashboard/1324> (accessed/modified new grid 29/06/2018)

- Winker, M., Vinnerås, B., Muskolus, A., Arnold, U., and Clemens, J., (2009) Fertiliser products from new sanitation systems: Their potential values and risks. *Bioresource Technology* 100, 4090–4096. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2009.03.024
- WSP (Water and Sanitation Program), (2007). *Community-led total sanitation in rural areas*, World Bank, New Delhi, India.
- Zaręba, A., Krzemińska, A., and Widawski, K., (2016) Green Urbanism for the Greener Future of Metropolitan Areas. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.*44, 052062. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/44/5/052062. <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/44/5/052062/pdf> (accessed 29/06/2018)